

1 **Impact of activation solutions on fresh and frozen-thawed sperm motility and**
2 **fertilization success for two species of migratory freshwater fishes**

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13
14 This is the accepted manuscript of the article:

15 França, T. S., Motta, N. C., Egger, R. C., Oliveira, A. V., & Murgas, L. D. S. (2020).
16 Impact of activation solutions on fresh and frozen-thawed sperm motility and fertilization
17 success for two species of migratory freshwater fishes. *Theriogenology*, 149, 6–15.
18 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2020.03.016>

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28 **Abstract**

29 Extracellular environment conditions, ionic concentration, pH, osmolality, and
30 temperature influence sperm activation and sperm quality. The aim of this study was to
31 evaluate the effects of different activating solutions on sperm quality and fertilization rate
32 of fresh and post-thaw sperm in *Brycon orbignyanus* and *Prochilodus vimboides*.
33 Activation solutions with ions: NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂ (150 mOsm kg⁻¹), without ions: glucose
34 (150 mOsm kg⁻¹) and water: reverse osmosis (RO) (~0 mOsm kg⁻¹) and tank water (TW)
35 were tested. In experiment 1, fresh sperm motility was activated in each activating
36 solution and motility rate (%), motility quality score (0-5), and motility duration (seconds)
37 were subjectively evaluated using a microscope. In experiment 2, sperm was
38 cryopreserved and post-thaw sperm quality was assessed in each activating solution.
39 Methyl glycol was used as cryoprotectant and for *B. orbignyanus* a solution of BTS® 5%
40 in water reverse osmosis - 325 mOsm kg⁻¹ was used as extender, while for *P. vimboides*
41 it was used a solution of glucose 5% in water reverse osmosis - 325 mOsm kg⁻¹. In straw,
42 cryoprotectant, extender, sperm were respectively 10%, 80% 10% (V/V). *B. orbignyanus*
43 fresh sperm activated in NaCl, KCl, glucose solutions, TW and RO yielded higher
44 averages for all the subjective parameters analysed. In fresh sperm of *P. vimboides* the
45 highest values were observed when glucose solution was used for sperm motility
46 activation, and the highest fertilization rates were observed in samples activated in
47 glucose or RO solutions. *B. orbignyanus* post-thaw sperm activated in TW (45.1%) or
48 RO (39.7%) presented the highest values for motility. The highest values of curvilinear
49 velocity (VCL) were observed using glucose (69.5 mm s⁻¹), NaCl (67 mm s⁻¹) and KCl
50 (68.4 mm s⁻¹), but the highest fertilization rates were observed when glucose (3.6%), RO
51 (3.5%) and TW (2.5%) were used. *P. vimboides* post-thaw sperm activated in glucose
52 solution presented the highest motility rate (41%), VCL (43.7 mm s⁻¹), fertilization rate
53 (18.2%) and hatching rate (13.7%). In order to achieve the best seminal quality,
54 fertilization and hatching rates in both fresh and post-thaw sperm, the glucose solution,
55 TW and RO are indicated for use as sperm motility activators in *B. orbignyanus*, whereas
56 for *P. vimboides* the glucose solution and RO are indicated.

57

58 **Keywords:** Activator; CASA; Fertilization; Characiformes; Fish

59

60 1. Introduction

61 *Brycon orbignyanus* (Characiformes) (Valenciennes, 1850) is a neotropical migratory
62 fish, distributed along the basin of the Parana, and Paraguay rivers [1]. This species
63 presents excellent aquaculture potential and is also considered a sporting species by
64 anglers. However, anthropic actions such as construction of hydroelectric dams,
65 pollution, and extractive fishing have caused a decline in the natural population of this
66 species, which is now considered an endangered species in some ecosystems [2].

67 *Prochilodus vimboides* (Characiformes) (Kner, 1859) is one of the 13 described species
68 of the genus *Prochilodus*. It is also a migratory fish, distributed in the Paraíba do Sul,
69 Jequitinhonha, Jucuruçu, Mucuri and Doce river basins, and its state of conservation is
70 considered vulnerable [3].

71 Fish spermatozoa are immobile within the testes and seminal plasma, and sperm motility
72 of freshwater fish begins when gametes are released in a hypotonic aquatic environment
73 [4]. In addition, activation of sperm motility is regulated by differences in the physical-
74 chemical characteristics of the activation medium and

75 seminal plasma [5], as ions (Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+}), pH, osmolality and temperature [4,6].
76 Therefore, the composition of the activating solution must be species-specific [7].

77 Neotropical migratory species are not able to reproduce naturally in captivity. Therefore,
78 artificial reproduction is necessary. Artificial reproduction with use of post-thaw sperm,
79 could be achieved with higher efficiency when proper activating solution is chosen [7-
80 15]. The activation can be performed with water (distilled, deionized and reverse osmosis)
81 with osmolality close to zero, or solutions containing only one salt (NaCl , KCl , NaHCO_3 ,
82 CaCl_2), or combinations of salts (MgSO_4 , Na_2HPO_4 , KH_2PO_4) and even solutions of
83 sugars (glucose, sucrose, mannitol). The purpose of using activating solutions is to
84 improve spermatozoa quality, mainly after the cryopreservation process [7]. It is known
85 that the cryopreservation process causes injury to the sperm cells, thus making it more
86 sensitive to alterations in the media, e.g. activating solutions with higher osmolality and
87 different ionic compositions [7].

88 Several studies have demonstrated the positive effect of ions on activating solutions on
89 sperm motility in cyprinids [9,10], salmonids [5,11], sturgeons [12,16] and characiforms
90 [7,8,13]. However, for the tropical migratory species *B. orbignyanus* and *P. vimboides*,
91 of the Characiformes order, sperm activating solutions that may allow higher sperm
92 quality have not yet been fully defined. Thus, the objective of the present study was to
93 define different activating solutions for fertilization using either fresh or post-thaw sperm

94 of two migratory species (*Brycon orbignyianus* and *Prochilodus vimboides*), which are
95 considered endangered and vulnerable populations.

96

97 **2. Materials and methods**

98

99 *2.1. Fish handling and sperm collection*

100

101 The handling of animals and the experiments were carried out in strict accordance with
102 institutional guidelines (Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee of the Federal
103 University of Lavras (UFLA), Lavras, MG, Brazil. Protocol N. 06/2017). *B. orbignyianus*
104 (males n = 10 and females n = 2) were selected from fish cultured in earthen ponds at the
105 Fish Culture Station of the Minas Gerais Power Company (CEMIG) in the city of Itutinga
106 (21°19'16"S; 44°36'54"W), Minas Gerais State, Brazil, during the spawning season
107 (January). *P. vimboides* (males n = 8 and females n = 2) were selected from fish cultured
108 in earthen ponds at the Agricultural Research Company of Minas Gerais (EPAMIG) in
109 the city of Leopoldina (21°28'34"S; 42°43'17"W), Minas Gerais State, Brazil, during the
110 spawning season (December).

111 For *B. orbignyianus* breeders, males (1.0 ± 0.1 kg of body weight), with detectable running
112 sperm under soft abdominal pressure received a single intraperitoneal dose of carp
113 pituitary extract (CPE; Argent Chemical Laboratories, Redmond, Washington, USA) at
114 1 mg kg^{-1} , 6 h prior to sperm collection. Females (2.0 ± 0.1 kg of body weight) with
115 bulging of the celomathic cavity and reddish urogenital papilla were induced with three
116 hormonal doses of CPE. A previous dose 48 h prior to collection at a dosage of 0.25 mg
117 kg^{-1} , the first effective dose at 0.5 mg kg^{-1} 18 h prior to collection and the second effective
118 dose at 5 mg kg^{-1} 6 h prior to oocytes extrusion.

119 The same selection procedures were performed for *P. vimboides*; males (0.224 ± 0.1 kg
120 of body weight) received a single intraperitoneal dose of CPE at 5 mg kg^{-1} . Females
121 (0.210 ± 0.01 kg of body weight) were induced with two hormonal doses of CPE. The
122 first dose at 0.5 mg kg^{-1} 20 h prior to collection and the second dose at 5 mg kg^{-1} 8 h prior
123 to oocytes extrusion. Both protocols are used in the reproduction routine of these species
124 at the Fish Culture Stations where the samples were collected.

125 Prior to sperm collection, the urogenital papilla and proximities were cleaned and dried
126 to avoid contamination by water, feces, urine, and blood. The sperm was collected in
127 graduated test tubes, the volume was recorded and the sample was stored in a cooler

128 containing chemical ice (~6-9 °C) for a maximum of 30 min. Oocytes were collected in
129 a dry plastic container and after weighing, 1 g of spawning was used for total estimated
130 oocytes.

131

132 2.2. *Initial evaluation of sperm and characterization of seminal plasma*

133

134 Immediately after collection, each sperm sample was subjectively evaluated under light
135 microscope (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo, Japan) at x 200 magnification, for its
136 contamination and motility rate, using a NaCl activating solution at 150 mOsm kg⁻¹. Only
137 samples with a motility above 80% were used for subsequent analyzes. For the ideal
138 sperm: oocytes ratio during fertilization, an aliquot of 1 mL of sperm was diluted (1:
139 1000) in citrate formaldehyde and the individual sperm concentration was performed
140 through the Neubauer chamber. Briefly, a 10 mL aliquot of the diluted sperm was added
141 to the chamber and observed using a light microscope (Olympus® CX22LED, Tokyo,
142 Japan) at x 40 magnification. Sperm concentration was calculated considering the number
143 of sperm cells visualized on five squares from the Neubauer chamber and the dilution.

144 An aliquot of approximately 0.5 mL of sperm from each male was collected in an
145 eppendorf tube and centrifuged (K14-0602 Kasvi, São José dos Pinhas, Brazil) at 2000 g
146 for 30 min. The collected seminal plasma (supernatant) was frozen (-20 °C) and
147 subsequently evaluated for pH by pH meter (DM22 Digimed, São Paulo, Brazil).
148 Osmolality was tested using a vapor pressure osmometer (Wescor Vapro 5520, Logan,
149 USA) as was ionic composition (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺) by means of an inductively
150 coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (Spectro Blue ICPOES, Kleve, Germany).

151

152 2.3. *Preparation of sperm activating solutions*

153

154 The activating solutions were classified into three categories. Ionic activating solutions:
155 sodium chloride (NaCl), potassium chloride (KCl), and calcium chloride (CaCl₂), non-
156 ionic activating solution: glucose, and water as activating solutions: reverse osmosis (RO)
157 water, and tank water (TW). The ionic activating solutions were prepared using reverse
158 osmosis water and only one salt. Either NaCl, KCl or CaCl₂ was added to the solution
159 and the osmolality adjusted to 150 mOsm kg⁻¹. The non-ionic activating solution were
160 composed of glucose (C₁₂H₂₂O₆), also prepared with reverse osmosis water and osmolality
161 adjusted to 150 mOsm kg⁻¹. The types of water used were RO water (at ~ 0 mOsm kg⁻¹)

162 and TW collected from breeding tanks (*B. orbignyana* at 139 mOsm kg⁻¹ and *P.*
163 *vimboides* at 114 mOsm kg⁻¹). All the chemicals were purchased from Vetec Química
164 Fina LTDA (Duque de Caxias, RJ, Brazil). Each solution was kept in 100 mL amber glass
165 bottles, stored in a refrigerator at 6e8 °C and used within 7 days. The concentration in
166 mM of the chemical compounds used, the ionic composition (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺)
167 and pH of the activating solutions tested are shown in Table 1.

168

169 2.4 *Experiment 1. subjective evaluation of fresh sperm in different activating solutions*

170

171 To evaluate the different activating solutions in the fresh sperm of *B. orbignyana* and *P.*
172 *vimboides*, a 2 mL aliquot of sperm from each male was individually activated in 20 mL
173 of each activating solution and evaluated in duplicate analyzes. Sperm motility rate was
174 subjectively assessed (expressed as a percentage of motile spermatozoa in relation to the
175 total), motility quality score was assigned using an arbitrary grading system ranging from
176 0 (no movement) to 5 (rapidly swimming sperm) [17] and duration of sperm motility
177 (seconds) were subjectively evaluated under a light microscope (Olympus® CX22LED,
178 Tokyo, Japan) at x 200 magnification.

179

180 2.5 *Experiment 2. cryopreservation and evaluation of post-thaw sperm through CASA*

181

182 The sperm of *B. orbignyana* was cryopreserved within 30 min after collection following
183 the methodology described by Maria et al. (2006) [18]. The freezing medium was
184 composed of BTS® 5% (Beltsville Thawing Solution™, Minitüb, Tiefenbach/Landshut,
185 Germany; 79.9% glucose, 12.7% sodium citrate, 2.7% EDTA, 2.7% NaHCO₃, 1.6% KCl,
186 and 0.4% gentamycin; 325 mOsm kg⁻¹); pH 7.6 as extender and methyl glycol
187 [CH₃O(CH₂)₂OH] (Vetec Química Fina Ltd., Duque de Caxias, Brazil) as cryoprotectant
188 agent. All samples were individually diluted in the freezing medium at a ratio of 1:8:1
189 (50 ml sperm (10% V/V) + 400 ml BTS® (80% V/V) + 50 ml methyl glycol (10% V/V)).
190 The sperm of *P. vimboides* was cryopreserved within 30 min after collection following
191 the methodology described by Oliveira (2015) [19]. The freezing medium was composed
192 of glucose 5% (325 mOsm kg⁻¹; Vetec Química Fina Ltd., Duque de Caxias, Brazil); pH
193 7.6 as extender and methyl glycol [CH₃O(CH₂)₂OH] (Vetec Química Fina Ltd., Duque
194 de Caxias, RJ, Brazil) as cryoprotectant agent. All samples were individually diluted in
195 the freezing medium at a ratio of 1:8:1 (50 ml sperm (10% V/V) + 400 ml glucose (80%

196 V/V) + 50 ml methyl glycol (10% V/V)).
197 Sperm samples were then loaded into 0.5 mL straws, frozen in a nitrogen vapor vessel
198 (Dry Vapor Vessel YDH-8, Cryofarm, Itu, SP, Brazil) at -170 °C for 24h (approximately
199 -36 °C min⁻¹) [18], and then transferred to a cryogenic tank (BioCane 34 Thermo Fisher
200 Scientific, Dubuque, Iowa, USA) at -196 °C. Straws (n = 3 straws per male) were
201 individually thawed in a 60 °C water bath (Water-bath MA 127, Marconi, São Paulo,
202 Brazil) for 8 s [20]. For both species, post-thaw sperm analyzes were carried out at the
203 Division of Physiology and Pharmacology of the Department of Veterinary Medicine,
204 Federal University of Lavras, Lavras, Minas Gerais.

205 Sperm motility rate and velocities were estimated using the CASA system (Computer-
206 Assisted Sperm Analyzer), following the methodology described by Viveiros et al. (2012)
207 [21]. Sperm motility was triggered in each activating solution at a ratio of 1:10 (1 ml post-
208 thaw sperm:10 ml activating solution) directly in a Makler™ counting chamber (Sefi-
209 Medical Instruments ltd, Haifa, Israel) placed under a phase contrast microscope
210 (Nikon™ Eclipse E200, Tokyo, Japan) at x 100 magnification, green filter and phase 1
211 position. The microscope was connected to a video camera (Basler Vision
212 Technologies™ A780-54FC, Ahrensburg, Germany) generating 50 images s⁻¹; video
213 recording started approximately 10 s post-activation. Each image was analysed using the
214 standard settings for fish by Sperm Class Analyser™ software (SCA™ 2013, Microptics,
215 S.L. Version 5.4, Barcelona, Spain). Motility rate, curvilinear velocity (VCL), average
216 path velocity (VAP) and straight line velocity (VSL) were considered for analysis.
217 Spermatozoon was considered immotile when velocity was <20 mm s⁻¹ of VAP. To
218 determine these parameters, each individual spermatozoon (n = 642 ± 330 for *B.*
219 *orbignyianus* and 1222 ± 368 for *P. vimboides*) was followed throughout the recorded
220 video images from which sperm trajectories were evaluated.

221 For *B. orbignyianus* 30 straws and for *P. vimboides* 24 straws (three per male) were
222 evaluated using each of the six activating solutions in duplicate analysis. The sequence
223 of the solutions was different among the three straws: for *B. orbignyianus* straw 1 - TW,
224 Glucose, NaCl, RO, CaCl₂, KCl; straw 2 - KCl, CaCl₂, RO, NaCl, Glucose, TW; straw 3
225 - CaCl₂, TW, Glucose, KCl, NaCl, RO, and in *P. vimboides* straw 1 - NaCl, Glucose, KCl,
226 CaCl₂, RO, TW; straw 2 - TW, RO, CaCl₂, KCl, Glucose, NaCl; straw 3 - CaCl₂, Glucose,
227 TW, RO, NaCl, KCl. During analyzes, sperm and activating solutions were maintained
228 at room temperature at 25 °C.

229

230 2.6 Fertilization using fresh and post-thaw sperm cryopreservation and evaluation of
231 post-thaw sperm through CASA

232

233 All procedures described below were performed for both species, first using fresh sperm
234 samples, and later for post-thaw sperm samples.

235 For fertilization tests, 0.1 g oocytes (averaged 100 oocytes in *B. orbignyana* and 81
236 oocytes in *P. vimboides*) were weighed into 50 mL disposable cups. Then, 5 mL of fresh
237 sperm from each male were added to the disposable cups to reach an ideal sperm:oocyte
238 ratio of $22\text{-}37 \times 10^5$ for *B. orbignyana* [22] and 57×10^5 for *P. vimboides*, which is
239 considered ideal for *Prochilodus lineatus* (unpublished results).

240 For fertilization tests of both species, the activation was promoted individually using each
241 activating solution tested in the same volume of 5 mL, comprising 60 samples for *B.*
242 *orbignyana* (6 activating solutions x 10 males) and 54 samples for *P. vimboides* (6
243 activating solutions x 8 males). After addition of the sperm activating agents, circular
244 motions were performed for 90 s and the oocytes were randomly transferred to
245 experimental incubators (2 L). The incubators were arranged in one tank with constant
246 renewal of water and oxygenation, where oocytes remained in movement.

247 The fertilization rate was determined 8 h after fertilization, when the blastopore closure
248 can be observed. All oocytes from each incubator were analysed using a trinocular
249 stereomicroscope (Q7740SZ-T, Quimis, Diadema, Brazil) at x 10 and the result given by
250 the formula: fertilization rate (%) = (number of fertilized oocytes/total number of oocytes)
251 x 100. The hatch rate was estimated 24 h after fertilization and was given by the following
252 formula: hatch rate (%) = (number of hatched larvae/total number of oocytes) x 100.

253

254 2.7 Statistical analysis

255

256 Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Shapiro-Wilk and Leven's tests
257 were used for normality of data distribution and homogeneity of variances respectively.
258 If data did not present the normal distribution and homogeneity of variances, the
259 transformation arcsine square was applied. For significant differences, ANOVA was
260 used, followed by Student-Newman-Keuls test. For motility quality score, a categorical
261 parameter, data were expressed as median, and statistical analysis was performed through
262 the Friedman test. Possible correlations among volume, sperm concentration, plasma
263 osmolality, plasma pH, and ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) were analysed by Pearson's

264 correlation test. The level of significance for all statistical tests was set to 5% ($p < 0.05$).
265 Statistical analyses were conducted with the R software version 3.3.2 (R Development
266 Core Team, 2016).

267

268 **3. Results**

269

270 *3.1. Seminal plasma and characteristics of fresh sperm characterization*

271

272 *B. orbignyana* seminal plasma osmolality was 381 ± 8 mOsm kg^{-1} and pH 8.03 ± 0.08 .
273 The sperm volume was 7.9 ± 3.2 mL and concentration of $5.68 \pm 0.93 \times 10^9$ spermatozoa
274 mL^{-1} . *P. vimboides* seminal plasma osmolality was 345 ± 16 mOsm kg^{-1} and pH $8.75 \pm$
275 0.22 . The sperm volume was 1.0 ± 0.4 mL and concentration of $34.39 \pm 20 \times 10^9$
276 spermatozoa mL^{-1} . The seminal plasma ionic composition of both species is shown in Fig.
277 1.

278 No significant correlations ($p > 0.05$) were observed among the parameters reported
279 above for *B. orbignyana*. For *P. vimboides* there was a positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) in
280 seminal plasma between the Ca^{2+} ion and pH, negative correlations ($p < 0.05$) were
281 observed between the Na^+ ion and pH, and between the K^+ ion and osmolality (Table 2).

282

283 *3.2. Analysis of fresh sperm and fertilization rate*

284

285 In *B. orbignyana*, samples activated in KCl, NaCl, RO, TW, and glucose solutions
286 yielded motility above 93%, when compared to samples activated in CaCl_2 solution
287 (71.1%) (Fig. 2A). Longer duration of motility was observed when samples were
288 activated in NaCl, KCl and glucose solutions (98.6-134.1 s), compared to those activated
289 in TW, RO, and CaCl_2 (30.3-44.6 s) (Fig. 2B). Higher motility quality score was observed
290 when activation was triggered in NaCl, KCl, RO, TW, and glucose solutions (5), in
291 relation to activation in CaCl_2 solution (4) (Fig. 2C). The samples presented fertilization
292 rate (0.6-3.4%) (Fig. 2D) and hatching rate (0.1-2.6%) (Fig. 2E) but did not differ among
293 the activating solutions ($p > 0.05$).

294 In *P. vimboides*, samples activated in KCl, NaCl, RO, TW, and glucose solutions yielded
295 sperm motility above 84%, when compared to samples activated in CaCl_2 solution (38%)
296 (Fig. 3A).

297 When sperm activation was triggered in glucose solution (356 s) samples yielded higher

298 duration of motility, which was shorter when samples were activated in TW, RO, and
299 CaCl₂ solutions (26-34 s) (Fig. 3B). Higher motility quality score was observed when
300 samples were activated in NaCl, RO and glucose solutions (5), than in those activated in
301 CaCl₂ solution (2) (Fig. 3C). The fertilization rate was higher in samples activated in
302 glucose solution and RO (16-15%), compared to those activated in NaCl and KCl and
303 CaCl₂ solutions (0-1.4%) (Fig. 3D). Only samples activated in glucose, RO and TW
304 solution presented hatching rate (4.6-7%), which did not differ ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 3E).

305

306 3.3. Post-thaw sperm analysis and fertilization rate of *B. orbignyana*

307

308 Higher sperm motility was observed in samples activated in TW (45.1%), compared to
309 those activated in NaCl, KCl, glucose (32.4-33.7%) and CaCl₂ solutions (8.7%) (Fig. 4A).
310 As the results were similar among velocities, only VCL data is displayed in Fig. 4B.
311 Activation in NaCl (67 mm s⁻¹ of VCL; 57.8 mm s⁻¹ of VAP; 49.2 mm s⁻¹ of VSL), KCl
312 (68.4 mm s⁻¹ of VCL; 58 mm s⁻¹ of VAP; 48.7 mm s⁻¹ of VSL) and glucose (69.5 mm s⁻¹
313 of VCL; 59.9 mm s⁻¹ of VAP; 49.6 mm s⁻¹ of VSL) solutions provided higher velocities.
314 For complete sperm velocity data, refer to Supplementary Table 1. When activation was
315 triggered in glucose solution, RO and TW (2.6-3.7%) samples yielded higher fertilization
316 rates, compared to those activated in KCl solution (0.5%, Fig. 4C). Similarly, higher
317 hatching rates were observed when samples were activated in glucose solution, RO and
318 TW (1.9-2.6%), compared to those activated in KCl solution (0.5%) (Fig. 4D).

319

320 3.4. Post-thaw sperm analysis and fertilization rate of *P. vimboides*

321

322 Sperm motility in samples activated in glucose solution (41%) was higher ($p < 0.05$) than
323 those activated in other solutions (Fig. 5A). In addition, motility in samples activated in
324 RO (31.1%) was higher than those activated in TW, KCl and CaCl₂ solutions (1.8-18.7%).
325 Higher VCL was observed in samples activated in glucose solution (43.7 mm s⁻¹), when
326 compared to samples activated in KCl, CaCl₂, RO and TW solutions (29.1-37 mm s⁻¹)
327 (Fig. 5B). Samples activated in TW (34.7 mm s⁻¹) presented higher VAP than those
328 activated in CaCl₂ solution (17.8 mm s⁻¹). Higher values of VSL occurred in samples
329 whose activation was triggered in glucose, NaCl, RO and TW solutions (19.9-24.8 mm s⁻¹)
330 ¹), compared to those activated in KCl (15 mm s⁻¹) and CaCl₂ (12.2 mm s⁻¹) solutions. For
331 complete sperm velocity data, refer to Supplementary Table 1. The glucose solution and

332 RO provided higher fertilization rate (9-18.2%) than NaCl and KCl solutions (0.6-0.7%)
333 and there was no fertilization rate in samples activated in CaCl₂ solution (Fig. 5C).
334 Similarly, higher hatching rates were observed when samples were activated in glucose
335 solution and RO (7-13.7%), compared to NaCl and KCl solutions (0.5-0.6%) (Fig. 5D).

336

337 4. Discussion

338 For externally fertilizing species, the microenvironment characteristics influence sperm
339 performance; therefore, it is advisable to adjust the composition of the medium during
340 artificial reproduction to increase spermatozoa fertilizing ability. The mechanisms that
341 trigger sperm motility activation have been described in salmonids, sturgeons and
342 cyprinids [4,11,15,16]. Although characiforms sperm activation process has been less
343 described, some studies have recently addressed the mechanisms in these fish and have
344 shown differences between fresh and post-thaw sperm activation [7,8,13].

345 In the present study, the seminal characteristics such as volume, osmolality, and sperm
346 concentration are consistent with the values usually observed by other authors for these
347 species. The genus *Brycon* is known to exhibit relatively high seminal volumes and low
348 sperm concentrations, while the genus *Prochilodus* is known for its low seminal volume
349 and high sperm concentrations. The values of volume of sperm collected and sperm
350 concentration are consistent with those observed in *B. orbignyanus* [17,18,23]. However,
351 in the present study seminal plasma yielded higher osmolality than the values observed
352 for this species [17,24]. Lower values of osmolality may be associated with lower ionic
353 concentration of seminal plasma and/or urine contamination. In *P. vimbooides*, similar
354 values of volume and sperm concentration were observed by Oliveira (2015) [19]. This
355 is the first study to report *P. vimbooides* seminal plasma osmolality, and the values are
356 close to those observed in *P. lineatus* [17].

357 Spermatozoa are known to remain immobile in the testis and seminal plasma, and plasma
358 constitution exerts important physiological functions, including survival and sperm
359 activation [4]. In seminal plasma, the concentration of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, and Cl⁻ ions
360 controls the internal osmotic balance, maintaining sperm immobility [25]. In this study,
361 it was verified that Na⁺ and K⁺ are the most abundant ions in the seminal plasma of *B.*
362 *orbignyanus* and *P. vimbooides*. Similar results have been reported for *B. orbignyanus* and
363 another species from the *Prochilodus* genus, the *P. lineatus* [24] and also for other teleosts
364 [26,27]. The concentration of the Ca²⁺ ion in the seminal plasma of *B. orbignyanus* and
365 *P. vimbooides* was higher than observed for salmonids (0.3-2.6 mM L⁻¹) [28] and lower

366 than those found in cyprinids (43.5 mM L^{-1}) [29,30]. One possible explanation for this
367 fact is that seminal plasma ionic concentration is species and intra-specific [31].
368 Hyposmotic solutions trigger freshwater species sperm motility, which is also influenced
369 by the activating medium ionic composition [31]. In the present study, all activating
370 solutions, with or without the presence of ions, were able to activate both species fresh
371 and post-thaw sperm motility. This was also observed in *P. lineatus*, *B. orbignyana* and
372 *Brycon insignis* [7,8,17]. This proves that both species spermatozoa are activated by
373 hyposmotic shock, which is caused by the hyposmotic aqueous medium in relation to
374 seminal plasma [4]. Some studies have shown that there is no difference in seminal quality
375 using activators with or without ions in the same osmolality [7,8,17]. However, the results
376 of the present study show that the composition of the activating solutions alters the quality
377 parameters of the fresh and post-thaw sperm in both species. This consequently affects
378 the fertilization rate. This difference can be explained by the different compositions of
379 the seminal plasma, mainly the concentration of K^+ , Na^+ e Ca^{2+} ions [7].
380 In both species, thawed sperm presented inferior quality than fresh samples. Furthermore,
381 it was observed that the same activating solution had different behaviours in the activation
382 of fresh and post-thaw sperm. This can be explained by the process of freezing and
383 thawing the sperm, which damages the sperm cells, possibly by changing the functions
384 of ion channels and/or membrane permeability [8]. Thus, the use of the best activation
385 solutions for each species is important to improve sperm quality in artificial fertilization.
386 The solutions containing NaCl and NaHCO_3 have been used for post-thaw sperm
387 activation in *Brycon insignis* [7,14], *Brycon orthotaenia* [32], and *Leporinus obtusidens*
388 [33]. The use of KCl activating solution, for Characiformes order, was only reported in
389 *B. insignis* post-thaw sperm [7]. However, it has already been reported in other orders
390 such as cypriniforms *Barbus barbus* [10], *Cyprinus carpio* [34] and perciforms *Perca*
391 *fluviatilis* [31]. *B. orbignyana* sperm, when activated by KCl , NaCl or non-ionic
392 activating solutions, yielded similar motility and velocities. Possibly, this species sperm
393 does not depend on the presence of Na^+ or K^+ to activate its motility. This is different
394 from salmonids and sturgeons, where the K^+ ion is the key to sperm motility activation
395 [12].
396 In *P. vimboides*, sperm motility, VCL and VSL using KCl solution were lower than those
397 using NaCl as the activating solution. This suggests that the composition of the activating
398 solution affects sodium-potassium exchange [7]. However, as the sperm was activated by
399 all other solutions, as in *B. orbignyana*, it suggests ions are not the trigger for *P.*

400 *vimboides* sperm motility activation. The difference in osmolality between the sperm and
401 the medium seem to be the main mechanism to trigger sperm motility in these species.
402 Thus, it is likely that the ions present in the medium are more important to its osmolality
403 rather than exerting direct influence on sperm motility [24]. In this way, this study
404 provides information on which components can be used to modulate medium osmolality
405 and provide better sperm performance during assisted reproduction, and which
406 components should be avoided.

407 Sperm samples activated in CaCl₂ solution yielded lower duration and motility rate, as
408 well as velocities and fertilization rate in both species, when compared to those activated
409 in the other activating solutions. A similar result was observed in a study with *C. carpio*,
410 where the lowest sperm motility occurred when the sperm was activated in a Ca²⁺ solution
411 [34]. In another study with *C. elongatus*, activating solutions containing 0-5 mM Ca²⁺ did
412 not affect sperm motility, however, activation in solutions containing 1-5 mM Ca²⁺,
413 produced the highest sperm velocities [35]. Possibly, the results observed when the CaCl₂
414 solution was used can be explained by the formation of sperm agglutinations, which is
415 common when this activating solution is used, and results in a marked decrease in sperm
416 motility and velocities. These agglutinations may have been caused by the high Ca²⁺
417 concentration in the solution, as observed in *Puntius javanicus* e *B. insignis* [7,36].

418 The glucose solution used had low Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations, as well as RO
419 and TW. The use of sperm-activating solutions based on sugars such as glucose, sucrose
420 and mannitol has already been reported in *B. orbignyanus*, *P. lineatus* [8,17], *B. insignis*
421 [7], *E. lucius* [37], and *C. elongatus* [35]. Activation of sperm motility at lower
422 osmolalities, such as in RO water, tends to produce high percentages of motility for a
423 short period, as observed for the two species studied here. Sperm exposure to lower
424 osmolality media may cause damage to the flagellum, which would explain the reduced
425 motility time [37,38].

426 Knowledge of sperm motility activation physiology allows for correct reproductive
427 management during artificial fertilization, both in fresh and post-thaw sperm. The results
428 presented in this study contribute to the improvement of fertilization protocols for these
429 two species, which are considered as endangered and vulnerable populations. The
430 presence of ions does not seem to be essential to triggering fresh and post-thaw sperm
431 motility of the two species under study. Thus, for *Brycon orbignyanus* fresh and post-
432 thaw sperm activating solutions containing the Ca²⁺ ion should be avoided. Whereas,
433 specifically for post-thaw sperm activation, non-ionic and water activating solutions are

434 better indicated for good sperm quality and satisfactory fertilization rates. For
435 *Prochilodus vimboides*, non-ionic and water solutions are better indicated for activating
436 fresh sperm, whereas glucose solution is most indicated used for post-thaw sperm
437 activation.

438

439 **Acknowledgements**

440

441 This study received funding from Brazilian Federal Agency for Support and Evaluation
442 of Graduate Education (CAPES) [grant number 88881.117641/2016-01], the Brazilian
443 National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) [grant number
444 304940/2014-3], FAPEMIG e Rede Mineira de Bioterismo [grant number RED 00009-
445 14]. This study is part of França's MSc dissertation. The authors thank Fishery Company
446 of the State of Minas Gerais (CEMIG) and Agricultural Research Company of Minas
447 Gerais (EPAMIG), Willian F. Carneiro (PhD student) for help with experiments, Ivo G.
448 Prado (CEMIG, Itutinga) for providing the broodfish, Jaílson M. Silva (CEMIG,
449 Itutinga), Jardel Peixoto (EPAMIG, Leopoldina), Geraldo Francisco (EPAMIG,
450 Leopoldina), José Lopes (EPAMIG, Leopoldina) and José do Carmo (EPAMIG,
451 Leopoldina) for assistance during fish selection.

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618 **Tables**

619

620 **Table 1.** Chemical concentration (mM) required to prepare the activating solutions and
 621 their ionic composition (mmol L⁻¹ = mM) used in fresh and post-thaw sperm of *Brycon*
 622 *orbignyanus* and *Prochilodus vimboides*. The ionic concentration of the activating agents
 623 was determined by an inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer. All
 624 solutions considered ionic and glucose were prepared using reverse osmosis water (~100
 625 mL) and adjusted to 150 mOsm kg⁻¹. Ionic solutions: NaCl = sodium chloride; KCl =
 626 potassium chloride; CaCl₂.2H₂O = calcium chloride dihydrate. Non-ionic solution:
 627 C₆H₁₂O₆ = D (+) anhydrous glucose (dextrose). Water: RO = reverse osmosis water; TW
 628 = tank water.

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Activating Solution	mM	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	pH
NaCl	79	46.3	9.6	0.3	1.1	7
KCl	80	3.1	82.4	0.2	0.8	8
CaCl ₂	66	4.1	7.0	17.67	0.7	7.6
Glucose	144	3.1	9.0	0.4	0.7	7.7
RO	–	4.9	8.5	0.4	0.8	7.7
TW (<i>B. orbignyanus</i>)	–	3.1	7.0	0.2	0.6	8.4
TW (<i>P. vimboides</i>)	–	5.6	7.0	0.1	0.6	8.4

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634 **Table 2**

635 Correlation matrix (Pearson's coefficient) of fresh sperm and seminal plasma
 636 characteristics of *Brycon orbignyanus* (n = 10 males) and *Prochilodus vimboides* (n = 8
 637 males).

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<i>B. orbignyanus</i>								
	Volume	Concentration	Osmolality	pH	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	
Volume	1.00							
Concentration	0.18	1.00						
Osmolality	0.18	-0.34	1.00					
pH	0.61	0.08	0.07	1.00				
Na ⁺	0.53	-0.34	0.42	0.31	1.00			
K ⁺	-0.03	-0.49	0.61	0.11	0.01	1.00		
Ca ²⁺	0.19	-0.04	0.15	0.16	-0.34	0.24	1.00	
Mg ²⁺	-0.48	0.35	0.12	-0.16	-0.25	0.15	-0.05	
<i>P. vimboides</i>								
	Volume	Concentration	Osmolality	pH	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
Volume	1.00							
Concentration	0.59	1.00						
Osmolality	-0.55	0.52	1.00					
pH	-0.81	-0.61	0.05	1.00				
Na ⁺	0.70	0.74	0.16	-0.96**	1.00			
K ⁺	0.48	-0.30	-0.99*	0.09	-0.29	1.00		
Ca ²⁺	-0.83	-0.19	0.47	0.88*	-0.75	-0.19	1.00	
Mg ²⁺	0.53	-0.05	-0.72	-0.16	-0.09	0.81	-0.33	1.00

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*p < 0.05. **p < 0.01. Units: Volume (mL), Concentration (x10⁹ spermatozoa mL⁻¹), Osmolality (mOsm kg⁻¹), Ionic concentration of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ (mmol L⁻¹)

641 **Figures**
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Fig. 1. Concentration of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ e Mg²⁺ ions (mmol L⁻¹ = mM) in the seminal plasma of *Brycon orbignyanus* (n = 10) (A) and *Prochilodus vimboides* (n = 8) (B). Bars indicate median e quartile. The ionic concentrations were determined by an inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer.

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Fig. 2. Fresh sperm motility rate (A), duration of motility (B), motility quality score (C), fertilization rate (D) and hatching rate (E) of *Brycon orbignyana* after activation in ionic, nonionic solutions and water. (A, B, D, E) bars indicate median \pm quartile. Means followed by different superscript differ ($p < 0.05$; Student-Newman-Keuls test). (C) Score 0 (no movement) to 5 (rapidly swimming sperm); bars indicate median \pm quartile. Medians followed by different superscript differ ($p < 0.05$; Friedman test).

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Fig. 3. Fresh sperm motility rate (A), duration of motility (B), motility quality score (C), fertilization rate (D) and hatching rate (E) of *Prochilodus vimboides* after activation in ionic, non-ionic solutions and water. (A, B, D, E) bars indicate median \bar{p} quartile. Means followed by different superscript differ ($p < 0.05$; Student-Newman-Keuls test). (C) Score 0 (no movement) to 5 (rapidly swimming sperm); bars indicate median \bar{p} quartile. Medians followed by different superscript differ ($p < 0.05$; Friedman test).

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Fig. 4. Post-thaw sperm motility rate (A), curvilinear velocity (VCL; B), fertilization rate (C) and hatching rate (D) of *Brycon orbignyanus* after activation in ionic, non-ionic solutions and water. Bars indicate median and quartile. Means followed by different superscript differ ($p < 0.05$; Student-Newman-Keuls test).

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705 **Fig. 5.** Post-thaw sperm motility rate (A), curvilinear velocity (VCL; B), fertilization rate
706 (C) and hatching rate (D) of *Prochilodus vimbooides* after activation in ionic, non-ionic
707 solutions and water. Bars indicate median \pm quartile. Means followed by different
708 superscript differ ($p < 0.05$; Student-Newman-Keuls test).